

an inhibitory factor caused the red-grained plants.

Single plant selection and progeny testing were carried out systematically and the nonsegregating red lines bulked and multiplied. The new line was designated Red Triveni and tested in replicated yield trials during the three main rice seasons 1985-86.

The new culture with red grain uniformly performed well during the three seasons (see table). In adaptive trials in farmers' fields in three districts

Performance of Red Triveni in wet, dry, and summer seasons. Pattambi, Kerala, India, 1985-86.

Variety	Days to 50% flowering			Grain yield (t/ha)		
	Summer	Kharif	Rabi	Summer 1985-86	Kharif 1986	Rabi 1986
Red Triveni	78	94	74	4.8	4.1	3.3
Triveni	78	94	78	4.4	3.8	2.7
Annappoorna	77	89	67	4.3	3.7	2.6
Rohini	76	99	65	4.3	3.8	2.4
LSD (P = 0.05)				ns	ns	0.2

in summer season 1987, Red Triveni yields averaged 6 t/ha (yields of the

original white-grained Triveni averaged 5.2 t/ha). □

A blast (Bl)-resistant and high-yielding early indica variety

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Fu 8-1 is a newly released semidwarf indica variety induced from variety 8004 with Co⁶⁰ r-ray (3.5 krad). It has 115-120 d duration, 1-2 d earlier than popular local variety Guang-Lu-Ai 4, with wide adaptability in Zhejiang,

Jiangxi, Hunan, and Hubei Provinces (26.0-31.0°N, 114-120°E).

The new variety performed well in the regional trials of Zhejiang Province in 1986 and 1987—average yields 7.5 t/ha, nearly 9% higher than Guang-Lu-Ai 4 (Table 1). Grain quality is also better.

An outstanding characteristic of Fu 8-1 is its widespectrum resistance to rice Bl caused by *Pyricularia oryzae*. In 1986 artificial inoculation tests, it was resistant to 26 and moderately resistant to 1 of 29 local isolates (Table 2). It also has good field resistance. □

Table 1. Some agronomic characteristics^a of Fu 8-1. Hangzhou, China, 1986-87.

Variety	Duration (d)	Plant ht (cm)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Grains (no./panicle)	1000-grain wt (g)	Seed set (%)	Yield ^a (t/ha)
Fu 8-1	114	75.8	472.26	69.7	32.2	76.6	7.5
Guang-Lu-Ai 4	114	67.4	533.73	66.7	25.2	78.1	6.9

^aMean of 7 sites.

Table 2. Reaction of Fu 8-1 to 29 *P. oryzae* isolates belonging to groups A to G.^a Hangzhou, China, 1986-87.

Variety	Reaction ^b																												
	A7		B11				B15				B3			B19		C15		D3			D7		E1		E3		G1		
	15-1	14-2	18-9	31-2	34-2	52-3	15-4	15-1	20-2	51-4	51-4	64-4	18-5	43-1	83-4	14-1	90-1	71-1	82-1	85-4	49-4	36-3	49-4	46-2	16-1	6-3	7-2	21-2	9-3
Fu 8-1	M	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	S	R	R	S	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R
Guang-Lu-Ai4	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	R	R	R	S	S	M	R	S	S	S	S	S

^aGrouping based on Chinese differentials. Each letter is followed by the race number in that group. ^bR = resistant, M = moderately resistant, S = susceptible.

OM91: an improved rice variety for high-production irrigated areas

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OM91 was found to be widely adapted in several provincial trials. It has higher

Table 1. Yield of OM91 at CLRRI, Omon Haugiang, Vietnam, 1984-86.

Variety	Yield (t/ha)					Average
	Dry season			Wet season		
	1983	1984	1985	1984	1985	
OM91	4.6	4.4	5.8	6.8	4.5	5.8
NN7A	4.8	3.9	5.7	6.3	4.5	5.0
LSD %	0.7	0.6	0.7	0.6	0.4	—
CV (%)	7.3	13.7	14.6	13.7	14.6	—